

1 **Biogas bioconversion into poly(3-hydroxybutyrate) by a mixed**
2 **microbial culture in a novel Taylor flow bioreactor**

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13 Graphical abstract

14

15 **Abstract**

16 Biogas-based biopolymer production represents an alternative biogas valorization route with
17 potential to cut down plastic pollution and greenhouse gas emissions. This study investigated
18 for the first time the continuous bioconversion of methane, contained in biogas, into poly(3-
19 hydroxybutyrate) (PHB) by a mixed methanotrophic culture using an innovative high mass-
20 transfer Taylor flow bioreactor. Following a hydrodynamic flow regime mapping, the
21 influence of the gas residence time and the internal gas recirculation on CH₄ abatement was
22 assessed under non nutrient limiting conditions. Under optimal operational conditions (gas
23 residence time of 60 min and internal gas recycling ratio of 17), the bioreactor was able to
24 support a CH₄ removal efficiency of 63.3%, a robust CH₄ elimination capacity (17.2 g-CH₄
25 m⁻³ h⁻¹) and a stable biomass concentration (1.0 g L⁻¹). The simultaneous CH₄ abatement and
26 PHB synthesis was investigated under 24-h:24-h nitrogen feast/famine continuous operation.
27 The cyclic nitrogen starvation and the Taylor flow imposed in the bioreactor resulted in a
28 relatively constant biomass concentration of 0.6 g L⁻¹ with PHB contents ranging from 11 to
29 32% *w w*⁻¹ (on a dry weight basis), entailing an average PHB productivity of 5.9 g-PHB m⁻³
30 d⁻¹ with an associated PHB yield of 19.8 mg-PHB g-CH₄⁻¹. Finally, the molecular analysis of
31 the microbial population structure indicated that type II methanotrophs outcompeted non-
32 PHB accumulating type I methanotrophs, with a heterotrophic-methanotrophic consortium
33 enriched in *Methylocystis*, *Hyphomicrobium*, *Rubinisphaeraceae* SH PL14 and
34 *Pseudonocardia*.

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36 **Keywords:** Biogas valorization, Biorefinery, Bioplastics, Mixed methanotrophic culture,
37 PHAs, Taylor flow bioreactor

38 1. Introduction

39 Biogas is one of the main by-products from the anaerobic digestion of organic waste
40 and wastewaters. Biogas is typically composed of a mixture of CH₄ (≈50–70%), CO₂ (≈30–
41 50%) and trace contaminants like H₂S, NH₃ and siloxanes (Muñoz et al., 2015). Methane
42 (CH₄) is the main valuable component in biogas due to its high calorific value and therefore
43 potential application as renewable energy vector (IEA, 2004). However, CH₄ generation may
44 also represent an environmental burden if not properly managed due to its global warming
45 potential (GWP) (≈25 folds the GWP of CO₂ in a time horizon of 100 years). For instance,
46 the European Union 27 member countries (EU-27) emitted ≈385.4 Mt of CH₄ as CO₂eq in
47 2019, an amount that must be rapidly reduced as a result of the recent EU methane mitigation
48 strategy (EEA (European Environmental Agency), 2021; European Commission, 2020). It is
49 estimated that around 56% of methane emissions are diluted, which cannot be used for
50 energy generation. These emissions mainly come from sewers, manure storage tanks, cattle
51 operation and ventilated coal mines (Cantera et al., 2018), , and severely contribute to global
52 warming and climate change.

53 Despite the feasible use of biogas as fuel for heat and electricity generation, according to
54 the EEA (2020), its 33 member countries still emitted 19.8 Mt of CH₄ as CO₂eq from landfills
55 in 2017 as a result of the limited economic viability of combined heat and power plants due to
56 their high investment, operational and maintenance costs (da Costa Gomez, 2013; Kaparaju
57 and Rintala, 2013). Indeed, biogas exhibits a levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) similar to
58 fossil fuels (0.05–0.19\$ KWh⁻¹), but recently higher than the LCOE of solar and wind power
59 (IRENA, 2021). In this context, there is an urgent need to develop innovative and cost-
60 competitive valorization routes for biogas in order to foster the economic sustainability of
61 anaerobic digestion and mitigate new potential CH₄ emissions.

62 The production of polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) using biogas as the feedstock has
63 been recently explored and might be competitive if properly optimized (Comesaña-Gándara
64 et al., 2022; López et al., 2018; Pérez et al., 2020). These biopolymers are considered a
65 sustainable substitute of fossil-based plastics owing to their biodegradability and their low
66 carbon footprint when produced from waste emissions such as biogas. Poly(3-
67 hydroxybutyrate) (PHB) is the most representative type of PHA synthesized by type II
68 methanotrophs under nutrient limiting conditions. In these organisms, CH₄ is firstly oxidized
69 by a methane monooxygenase to then enter the serine pathway, where deprivation of
70 nutrients such as nitrogen and phosphate induce the synthesis and intracellular accumulation
71 of PHB (Cal et al., 2016; Pieja et al., 2011; Rodríguez et al., 2020a). To date, pure cultures
72 have been mainly used as workhorse in continuous bioreactors converting CH₄ into PHB
73 (García-Pérez et al., 2018; Rodríguez et al., 2020b), which represents an ecological and
74 economical barrier to further scale up this process. Mixed cultures typically show a more
75 robust performance against environmental fluctuations and process upsets than pure cultures,
76 and show negligible differences on CH₄ abatement at different temperatures, O₂
77 concentrations and nutrients availability (Chidambarampadmavathy et al., 2015; Karthikeyan
78 et al., 2015; Pérez et al., 2019a, 2019b).

79 Despite the significant advances carried out in this field over the past 10 years, a cost-
80 effective PHB production using biogas as feedstock and type II methanotrophs as workhorse
81 must overcome key technological barriers. Thus, high energy inputs and bioreactor volumes
82 are needed to achieve an effective CH₄ mass transfer from the gas to the aqueous phase,
83 which can jeopardize the economic feasibility of the process. To date, to the best of the
84 authors' knowledge, only bubble column, fluidized bed and stirred tank bioreactors have been
85 operated at lab and pilot scale for the simultaneous abatement of CH₄ and production of PHB

86 (Chidambarampadmavathy et al., 2015; García-Pérez et al., 2018; Pfluger et al., 2011;
87 Rodríguez et al., 2020b). Thus, there is an urgent need to develop and assess novel bioreactor
88 configurations for the continuous CH₄ abatement and biopolymer production (Karthikeyan et
89 al., 2015). In this regard, Taylor flow reactors are multi-capillary channels systems where
90 sequences of gas bubbles and liquid slugs move in an upflow co-current mode (this is why
91 the terms Taylor flow and slug flow can be used interchangeably), which can support gas-
92 liquid volumetric mass transfer coefficients one order of magnitude higher than conventional
93 reactors due to the internal recirculation within the liquid slug and gas bubble, the large
94 specific surface area, and the small diffusion paths (Gupta et al., 2010; Rocha-Rios et al.,
95 2013; Rodríguez et al., 2020c). This innovative reactor configuration has been tested in
96 several different fields (e.g., biomedical, oil and gas industry, chemical processing, and so on
97 (Gupta et al., 2010) with promising results but never tested in biogas-based biopolymer
98 production applications.

99 This study assessed for the first time the performance of a novel Taylor flow bioreactor
100 during biogas bioconversion into PHB using a mixed methanotrophic culture under
101 continuous mode. The Taylor flow regime was initially mapped, and the influence of gas
102 residence time and internal gas recycling on the CH₄ elimination capacity of the Taylor flow
103 bioreactor was investigated. This study also evaluated the continuous production of PHB
104 from biogas under optimal CH₄ mass transfer conditions using a mixed methanotrophic
105 culture subjected to nitrogen feast/famine cycles. Finally, the structure of the microbial
106 community supporting PHB synthesis from biogas under steady state was also investigated.

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110 2. Materials and methods

111 2.1 Chemicals

112 The mineral salt medium (MSM) used during the entire experiment, unless otherwise
113 specified, consisted of (mg L⁻¹): 409.5 KH₂PO₄; 534 Na₂HPO₄·12H₂O; 2000 KNO₃; 200
114 MgCl₂·6H₂O; 110 CaCl₂·2H₂O; 2.76 Na₂EDTA·2H₂O; 10 CuSO₄·5H₂O; 5 FeSO₄·7H₂O; 4
115 ZnSO₄·7H₂O; 0.15 H₃BO₃; 0.27 CoCl₂; 0.2 MnCl₂·4H₂O; 0.1 NiCl₂·6H₂O and vitamins
116 (biotin, nicotinamide, p-aminobenzoic acid and pantothenic acid). Potassium nitrate was
117 obtained from Cofarcas S.A. (Burgos, Spain), whereas the rest of the constituents required for
118 the preparation of the MSM were acquired from PanReac AppliChem (Barcelona, Spain).
119 Gas cylinders of CH₄ (purity ≥ 99.995%), O₂ (≥ 99.5%) and synthetic biogas (70% CH₄, 30%
120 CO₂) were purchased from Abelló Linde S.A. (Barcelona, Spain). The commercial Poly(3-
121 hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV, with a PHV content of 12% mol) used for
122 the preparation of standard biopolymer solutions in chloroform was purchased from Sigma-
123 Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA).

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125 2.2 Inocula

126 An enriched methanotrophic culture obtained from *Sphagnum* (a peat moss rich in
127 methanotrophs) and an enriched methanotrophic culture mixture obtained from *Sphagnum* +
128 activated sludge, with the ability to synthesize PHB under nitrogen limitation (Pérez et al.,
129 2019b), were mixed with a pure culture of the type II methanotroph *Methylocystis hirsuta*
130 CSC1 (DSM 18500) (Rodríguez et al., 2020a). The three methanogenic cultures were
131 independently inoculated in duplicate (under sterile conditions for *M. hirsuta*) at 5% (v v⁻¹) in
132 120 mL bottles (19 mL of MSM + 1 mL of inoculum) containing a 67%/33% O₂:CH₄
133 atmosphere to ensure oxygen non-limiting conditions, given that given that previous reports

134 have identified an minimum of $\sim 1.5 \text{ mol O}_2 \text{ mol CH}_4^{-1}$ for an effective CH_4 oxidation and
135 PHB accumulation (Rodríguez et al., 2020a). The cultures were incubated at 30°C and 250
136 rpm in an orbital shaker (MaxQ4000; Thermo Scientific, USA) for ~ 14 days. The headspace
137 of the gas-tight bottles was daily replaced with a fresh 67%/33% ($v v^{-1}$) $\text{O}_2:\text{CH}_4$ atmosphere.
138 The cultures were transferred to six 2.1 L gas-tight serum bottles (containing 380 mL of
139 MSM + 20 mL of inoculum) and incubated at 25°C and 300 rpm for 10 days using a similar
140 67%/33% ($v v^{-1}$) $\text{O}_2:\text{CH}_4$ headspace (the headspace of all the bottles was replaced with the
141 initial O_2/CH_4 atmosphere on day 6). Prior inoculation, the cultures were centrifuged and
142 resuspended in fresh MSM to a final volume of 600 mL and to a final biomass concentration
143 of 7.5 g TSS L^{-1} .

144

145 *2.3 Experimental setup*

146 A 6 L (working volume) Taylor flow bioreactor with internal gas recirculation was used
147 in this work (Fig. 1). The bioreactor consisted of two polyvinyl chloride (PVC) tanks,
148 containing the methanotrophic culture in aqueous suspension, interconnected by 25 glass
149 circular capillary tubes with an internal diameter of 3 mm and length of 1.5 m. The lower
150 tank was constructed with a butyl perforated membrane to allow the sparging of a gas
151 mixture composed of atmospheric air and synthetic biogas. The biogas stream was regulated
152 by a mass flow controller (GFC17, AalborgTM, USA) to ensure a CH_4 concentration of 4%
153 (26.2 g m^{-3}), whereas atmospheric air was supplied by an air compressor (PUSKA COMBA
154 3200 II). A water condenser (kept at 10°C) was installed at the internal gas recirculation line
155 in order to prevent operational problems derived from water condensation. A ESPA Tecno 05
156 2M centrifugal pump was used to recycle the cultivation broth. Internal gas recirculation was

157 carried out using a Watson-Marlow 520S[®] peristaltic pump (WMFTG, UK). The Taylor flow
158 bioreactor was operated at 25°C in a temperature-controlled room.

159
160 **Fig. 1.** Photograph (A) and sketch (B) of the innovative Taylor flow bioreactor used to produce
161 PHB from synthetic biogas by a mixed methanotrophic culture. Slug flow regime is shown in
162 a zoom-in. Air compressor (1), synthetic biogas tank (2), mixing chamber (3), gas inlet (4),
163 butyl membrane (5), 3-mm capillary tubes (6), biomass containing chamber (7), gas outlet (8),
164 gas recirculation line (9), condenser (10), gas compressor (11), liquid sampling port (12), liquid
165 recirculation line (13), hydraulic pump (14).

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169 *2.4 Taylor flow regime mapping*

170 The mapping of flow regimes in the reactor was performed using air as the gas phase
171 and MSM as the liquid phase by systematically varying the air flow rates (0.9–9.9 L min⁻¹)
172 and MSM flow rates (3–10 L min⁻¹). In addition, the pressure in the inlet gas line was
173 measured to later calculate the gas flow rate and upflow gas velocities at atmospheric
174 pressure. The hydrodynamic regime in the tubes was video-recorded and analysed afterwards
175 to elucidate the occurrence of Taylor flow (Rocha-Rios et al., 2013).

176

177 *2.5 Influence of gas flow rate and internal gas recycling on CH₄ abatement in a Taylor Flow*
178 *bioreactor*

179 The influence of gas flow rates (0.9, 1.8 and 3.6 L min⁻¹) achieved without gas
180 recirculation (inlet flow corresponding to the total gas flow) and with internal gas
181 recirculation (inlet gas flow × recirculation ratio + inlet gas flow corresponding to the total
182 gas flow) on CH₄ biodegradation was evaluated at a constant liquid recirculation flow rate of
183 7 L min⁻¹ (which guaranteed Taylor flow regime according to the flow regime map
184 performed). The duration of each operational stage was set by the achievement of stable CH₄
185 elimination capacities (ECs). Table 1 depicts the experimental design. Aliquots of 500 mL of
186 MSM were daily exchanged to ensure nutrients availability, resulting in a dilution rate of
187 0.083 d⁻¹. An abiotic test was conducted to ensure the absence of any abiotic CH₄ degradation
188 mechanism and the gas tightness of the bioreactor. CH₄, CO₂ and O₂ concentrations in the
189 inlet and outlet gas streams were daily determined by GC-TCD using 100 µL samples drawn
190 with a Hamilton® GASTIGHT® syringe (Hamilton Co., USA). Aliquots of 40 mL from the
191 cultivation broth were daily taken to measure the pH, optical density (OD) and the
192 concentration of total suspended solids (TSS) as a biomass concentration proxy, dissolved

193 total organic carbon (TOC), dissolved total nitrogen (TN), and nitrate (NO_3^-) and nitrite
 194 (NO_2^-) concentrations.

195 **Table 1.** Experimental conditions tested during the optimization of CH_4 abatement.

Test no.	Total gas flow rate (L min^{-1})	Inlet gas flow rate (L min^{-1})	Recirculation ratio ^a	EBRT ^b (min)	Virtual EBRT ^c (min)	Inlet CH_4 loading rate ^d ($\text{g CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$)
1.1		0.9	0.0	6.7	6.7	236
1.2	0.9	0.1	8.0	60.0	6.7	26.2
1.3		0.2	3.5	30.0	6.7	52.4
2.1		1.8	0.0	3.3	3.3	471.6
2.2	1.8	0.1	17.0	60.0	3.3	26.2
2.3		0.2	8.0	30.0	3.3	52.4
3.1		3.6	0.0	1.7	1.7	943.2
3.2	3.6	0.1	35.0	60.0	1.7	26.2
3.3		0.2	17.0	30.0	1.7	52.4

196 a-Recirculation ratio [R]: the internal recirculation gas flow rate divided by the inlet gas flow rate.

197 b-Empty bioreactor residence time [EBRT]: the bioreactor volume divided by the inlet gas flow rate.

198 c-Virtual EBRT: the bioreactor volume divided by the total gas flow rate.

199 d-Inlet CH_4 loading rate: mass of methane supplied per unit of bioreactor volume and time.

200 All conditions were tested at a constant liquid recirculation flow rate of 7 L min^{-1} .

201

202 *2.6 Simultaneous methane abatement and PHB production under cyclic nitrogen feast/famine* 203 *operation*

204 The assessment of the continuous production of PHB from biogas was divided into
 205 three operational stages. During stage I, the Taylor-flow bioreactor was operated under
 206 nitrogen sufficient conditions at an internal gas flow rate of 1.8 L min^{-1} (recirculation ratio =
 207 17) and an inlet gas flow rate of 0.1 L min^{-1} for 11 days to ensure a stable methane
 208 elimination. Aliquots of 500 mL of cultivation broth were daily exchanged with fresh MSM.
 209 During stage II, the daily exchange of fresh MSM was suppressed for the following 9 days to
 210 ensure nitrogen limiting conditions in the Taylor flow bioreactor, which was operated under
 211 similar gas operational conditions to stage I. During stage III, nitrogen feast famine cycles of

212 24-h:24-h were applied for 28 days to induce the biosynthesis of PHB under similar gas
213 operational conditions to stage II. Thus, the supply of 0.5 L of MSM containing a nitrogen
214 concentration of 165.3 mg L⁻¹ (estimated to support biomass growth for 24 h based on the
215 prevailing CH₄-EC) was only carried out every two days to induce nitrogen limiting
216 conditions for 24 h (D = 0.042 d⁻¹). CH₄, CO₂ and O₂ concentrations in the inlet and outlet
217 gas streams were daily determined by GC-TCD using 100 µL samples drawn with a
218 Hamilton® GASTIGHT® syringe (Hamilton Co., USA). Aliquots of 40 mL from the
219 cultivation broth were daily taken to measure the PHB content in the methanotrophic
220 biomass, pH, OD, and the concentrations of TSS, TOC, TN, NO₂⁻ and NO₃⁻.

221

222 *2.7 Analytical procedures*

223 CH₄, CO₂ and O₂ gas concentrations were measured in a gas chromatograph coupled
224 with a thermal conductivity detector (Bruker 430, Bruker Corporation, USA) and equipped
225 with CP-Molsieve 5A and CP-PoraBOND Q columns according to (Carmona-Martínez et al.,
226 2021). The outlet gas flow rate was measured by using the water volume displacement
227 method. TSS concentration was quantified according to the 2540 method (APHA et al., 2017)
228 using 0.45 µm pore size filters (Merck, Germany). Optical density was measured at 600 nm
229 using a Spectrostar Nano (BMG Labtech, Germany). A Basic 20 pH meter (Crison, Spain)
230 was used for the measurement of pH. TN and TOC concentrations were determined in a
231 TOC-V analyzer equipped with a Shimadzu TNM-1 unit. NO₂⁻ and NO₃⁻ concentrations were
232 measured by ion chromatography using a Waters 432 HPLC conductivity detector (Waters
233 Corporation, USA) according to Guenka Scarcelli et al. (2021). Finally, PHB concentration
234 was determined using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) following digestion
235 and extraction according to Rodríguez et al. (2020a). The structure of the microbial

236 communities was analysed from two samples taken at the beginning of the bioreactor
 237 operation and at the end of the PHB production experiment. This analysis was carried out by
 238 following the 16S metagenomic sequencing library Illumina 15044223 B protocol. The
 239 region V3-V4 of the 16S rRNA gene was amplified using the primer set 341F-805R
 240 (Klindworth et al., 2013). The sequencing data obtained were analysed into the QIIME2
 241 platform (Bolyen et al., 2019). Clean amplicon sequencing variants (ASVs) were annotated
 242 against NCBI 16S rRNA database version 2021 at a 97% similarity, while SILVA database
 243 v.138 was used for those ASVs assigned with < 97% identity. Data was normalized using
 244 rarefaction technique from Phyloseq R package to perform alpha diversity analysis (Weiss et
 245 al., 2017). Shannon and Simpson indexes were calculated using vegan R package (Oksanen et
 246 al., 2020).

247

248 2.8 Performance indicators

249 The CH₄ elimination capacity (EC), CH₄ removal efficiency (RE), volumetric CO₂
 250 production rate (*RCO₂*) and PHB productivity were calculated using equation (1), (2), (3) and
 251 (4), respectively:

$$252 \quad EC = \frac{Q \cdot (CH_4 \text{ in} - CH_4 \text{ out})}{V} \quad (1) \text{ [g CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}]$$

$$253 \quad RE = \frac{(CH_4 \text{ in} - CH_4 \text{ out})}{CH_4 \text{ in}} \times 100 \quad (2) \text{ [%]}$$

$$254 \quad RCO_2 = \frac{Q \cdot (CO_2 \text{ out} - CO_2 \text{ in})}{V} \quad (3) \text{ [g CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}]$$

$$255 \quad PHB \text{ productivity} = TSS \cdot PHB \cdot D \quad (4) \text{ [g PHB m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}]$$

256 where, CH_{4 in} and CH_{4 out} stand for the inlet and outlet CH₄ concentrations (g m⁻³), CO_{2 in} and
 257 CO_{2 out} are the inlet and outlet CO₂ concentrations (g m⁻³), *Q* is the inlet gas flow rate (m³ h⁻¹)
 258 ¹), *V* is the bioreactor working volume (m³), TSS is the biomass concentration (g m⁻³), PHB is

259 the content of biopolymer in the biomass (% $w w^{-1}$ of cell dry weight (CDW) expressed in the
260 fraction form) and D is the dilution rate (d^{-1}).

261

262 **3. Results and discussion**

263 *3.1 Taylor flow regime mapping*

264 Three main flow regimes were identified from the flow regime mapping performed by
265 varying the gas and liquid superficial flow rates, i.e., bubbly, churn and Taylor (or slug)
266 patterns. The presence of gas-liquid segmented flow hydrodynamics (Taylor bubble flow)
267 was clearly observed in the medium range of tested flow superficial rates of liquid and gas
268 streams (Fig. 2). In contrast, bubbly and churn flow patterns were observed at a combination
269 of low gas ($< 0.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) and liquid superficial velocities ($< 0.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$), and high gas ($1.28 - 1.5$
270 m s^{-1}) and liquid superficial velocities ($0.65 - 1.0 \text{ m s}^{-1}$), respectively. To ensure Taylor flow
271 regime, the liquid recirculation flow rate was set at 7 L min^{-1} (0.66 m s^{-1}), while the total gas
272 flow rate was varied in the range of 0.9 to 3.6 L min^{-1} ($0.08 - 0.34 \text{ m s}^{-1}$). Comparatively,
273 Rocha-Rios et al. (2013) found bubbly flow conditions in a single capillary system at low gas
274 velocities ($1.7 \times 10^{-2} - 2.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m s}^{-1}$) in combination with liquid superficial velocities in
275 the range of $6.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.1 \times 10^{-1} \text{ m s}^{-1}$, and churn flow patterns when combining high gas
276 superficial velocity ($4.0 \times 10^{-2} - 1.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ m s}^{-1}$) with liquid superficial velocities in the
277 range of $2.5 \times 10^{-2} - 4.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ m s}^{-1}$. At this point it must be highlighted the inherent
278 difficulty to compare the gas-liquid flow regime maps found in the literature since those are
279 reactor specific (Kreutzer et al., 2005). Indeed, the prevailing behavior of two-phase gas-
280 liquid flow in a given microchannel depends on several parameters such as the fluid
281 properties, flow rates, ratio of phases, channel geometry, as well the material and roughness

282 of the microchannels and pressure and temperature (Gupta et al., 2010; Rocha-Rios et al.,
283 2011).
284

285
286 **Fig. 2.** Map of the gas-liquid flow regimes as a function of the gas and liquid velocities in the
287 vertical, circular capillary microtubes. Black diamonds represent Taylor bubble flow while
288 grey diamonds stand for bubbly and churn flow regimes.

289
290 *3.2 Influence of gas flow rate and internal gas recycling on CH₄ abatement in a Taylor Flow*
291 *bioreactor*

292 The continuous biodegradation of CH₄ in a Taylor flow reactor by a mixed
293 methanotrophic culture was evaluated with and without gas recirculation under non-limiting
294 nutrients conditions. In the absence of internal gas recycling, a gas flow rate of 0.9 L min⁻¹
295 entailed a steady state CH₄-EC of 30.1 ± 4.5 g CH₄ m⁻³ h⁻¹, corresponding to a CH₄-RE of
296 13.0 ± 1.8%. A further increase in the gas flow rate to 1.8 L min⁻¹ resulted in the highest EC
297 observed of 49.5 ± 2.4 g CH₄ m⁻³ h⁻¹ with an associated CH₄-RE of 10.1 ± 0.6%, suggesting

298 that mass transfer limitations constrained CH₄ abatement rather than biological activity.
299 Indeed, RCO_2 increased from 38.2 ± 13.6 to 82.9 ± 6.1 g m⁻³ h⁻¹ when the gas flow rate was
300 doubled from 0.9 to 1.8 L min⁻¹, the latter corresponding to a mineralization ratio ($RCO_2/EC-$
301 CH₄) of 1.7, in accordance with those found by García-Pérez et al. (2018). This enhanced
302 driving force caused a better CH₄ mass transfer performance, thus favouring CH₄
303 bioavailability and consequently its further utilization by the mixed methanotrophic culture
304 (Pérez et al., 2019b). However, a higher total gas flow rate (3.6 L min⁻¹) led to a high
305 turbulence within the bioreactor, which caused a rapid stripping of the biomass and a severe
306 shear stress on the microbial community, thus impairing the CH₄-EC, which remained at 40.7
307 ± 4.0 g CH₄ m⁻³ h⁻¹ with an associated CH₄-REs of $3.9 \pm 0.6\%$.

308 Under gas recirculation conditions, the CH₄-EC of the Taylor flow bioreactor increased
309 when increasing both the inlet gas flow rate and the internal gas recirculation flow rate.
310 Hence, steady state CH₄-ECs of 13.4 ± 1.2 , 17.2 ± 1.9 and 21.1 ± 2.4 g CH₄ m⁻³ h⁻¹ (with
311 associated CH₄-REs of 50.6 ± 2.5 , 63.34 ± 0.9 and 71.31 ± 1.4 %, respectively) were
312 recorded at total gas flow rates of 0.9, 1.8 and 3.6 L min⁻¹, respectively, operating at an inlet
313 gas flow rate of 0.1 L min⁻¹ with internal gas recirculation. Similarly, steady state CH₄-ECs of
314 20.1 ± 2.0 , 26.7 ± 1.6 , and 29.15 ± 3.8 g CH₄ m⁻³ h⁻¹ (corresponding to CH₄-REs of $35.5 \pm$
315 3.1 , 46.2 ± 1.9 and $50.4 \pm 6.6\%$) were observed at a constant inlet gas flow rate of 0.2 L min⁻¹
316 under an internal gas recirculation flow rates supporting total gas flow rates of 0.9, 1.8, and
317 3.6 L min⁻¹, respectively (see Fig. 3). Thus, the increase in the inlet diluted biogas flow rate
318 from 0.1 to 0.2 L min⁻¹ supported a higher CH₄ concentration gradient between the gas and
319 liquid phases at the expenses of lower CH₄-REs. It has been previously demonstrated that the
320 volumetric mass transfer coefficient for CH₄ (K_{La}) can be enhanced by applying internal gas
321 recycling, which decouples the real biogas residence time from the gas-liquid turbulence

322 within the reactor (Estrada et al., 2014; Rocha-Rios et al., 2011). However, as previously
323 mentioned, process operation at a total flow rate of 3.6 L min⁻¹ caused biomass stripping and
324 a severe shear stress inside the bioreactor due to the high turbulence created. This
325 phenomenon was also observed at a lower extent when operating at an inlet flow rate of 0.2 L
326 min⁻¹ and a total gas flow rate of 3.6 L min⁻¹ (recirculation ratio = 17), likely due to the
327 acclimation of the microbial community to the gas shear stress (see Supplementary material).
328 The CH₄-ECs observed in this study were endorsed by the recorded *RCO*₂ while working at
329 gas flow rates of 0.9 and 1.8 L min⁻¹ but this pattern was not observed when working at a gas
330 flow rate of 3.6 L min⁻¹ likely due to the decrease in biomass concentration (see Fig. 3 and
331 Fig. S1). In this context, steady state CH₄-ECs were achieved at biomass concentrations of ≥
332 1 g L⁻¹, except for the operational stages encountering the aforementioned biomass stripping
333 and shear stress phenomena, thus confirming that CH₄-ECs were only affected by CH₄
334 transport and not by microbial activity.

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337

338

339 **Fig. 3.** Influence of total gas flow rate on steady state CH₄-EC (A), CH₄-RE (B) and RCO₂ (C)
 340 in tests conducted with no internal gas recirculation (blacks bars), and with internal gas
 341 recirculation at inlet gas flow rates of 0.1 L min⁻¹ (gray bars) and 0.2 L min⁻¹ (white bars).

342

343 Comparatively, the maximum CH₄-EC herein recorded (49.5 ± 2.4 g CH₄ m⁻³ h⁻¹) at an
 344 EBRT of 3.3 min was higher than those achieved in packed bed biofilm reactors devoted to
 345 the aerobic treatment of diluted CH₄ emissions. For instance, (Nikiema et al., 2005) achieved
 346 a maximum CH₄-EC of 29.2 g CH₄.m⁻³ h⁻¹ in a biofilter (BF) operated at an inlet CH₄
 347 concentration of 0.7% and an EBRT of 4.3 min with a mixed methanotrophic culture.
 348 Likewise, Avalos Ramirez et al. (2012) reported a maximum CH₄-EC of 21 g CH₄ m⁻³ h⁻¹ in a
 349 biotrickling filter (BTF) operated at a constant inlet CH₄ concentration of 4.8 g m⁻³ (inlet load

350 of $61.8 \text{ g CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$) and an EBRT of 4.2 min with a mixed methanotrophic culture.
351 However, the CH_4 -ECs herein obtained were in agreement with the elimination capacities
352 reported in suspended growth reactors. For instance, Rodríguez et al. (2020b) reported CH_4 -
353 ECs in a bubble column bioreactor (BCB) of $49 - 74 \text{ g CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ at an EBRT of 30 min
354 using a pure culture of *M. hirsuta* CSC1 at a CH_4 concentration of 14% ($v v^{-1}$). The
355 significantly higher EBRTs (10 folds higher) along with the higher CH_4 gas-liquid
356 concentration gradient likely explain the slightly higher CH_4 -ECs obtained by Rodríguez et
357 al. (2020b). García-Pérez et al. (2018) achieved a maximum CH_4 -EC of $18.7 \text{ g CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ in
358 a BCB operated with a pure culture of *M. hirsuta* at an EBRT of 60 min and a virtual EBRT
359 of 4 min, operational conditions similar to those supporting the maximum CH_4 -EC in the
360 present work. Rocha-Rios et al. (2009) recorded a higher maximum CH_4 -EC of $106 \text{ g CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3}$
361 h^{-1} in a stirred-tank reactor (STR) working at an EBRT of 4.8 min, 800 rpm and a CH_4
362 concentration of 1% ($v v^{-1}$) using a mixed methanotrophic culture and 10% of silicone oil to
363 improve CH_4 mass transfer to the methanotrophic broth. However, STRs typically exhibit
364 significantly high energy demands caused by the need to maintain high stirring rates to
365 promote CH_4 gas-liquid mass transfer (Rodríguez et al., 2020c).

366 On the other hand, higher CH_4 -REs were supported when the inlet load of biogas was
367 decreased and when the internal gas recirculation rate was increased. The maximum CH_4 -RE
368 recorded in this work, $71.1 \pm 1.4\%$ at an EBRT of 60 min, a virtual EBRT of 1.7 min and an
369 inlet load of $26.2 \text{ g CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$, was in accordance with the RE values found in the literature.
370 For instance, García-Pérez et al. (2018) achieved a maximum CH_4 -RE of 75% at an EBRT of
371 60 min, a virtual EBRT of 4 min and an inlet load of $24 \text{ g CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$. Rodríguez et al.
372 (2020b) recorded a maximum CH_4 -RE of 70%, achieved at a ≈ 2 -fold inlet methane load (59 g

373 CH₄ m⁻³ h⁻¹) and an EBRT of 60 min. Finally, Rocha-Rios et al. (2010) obtained a maximum
374 CH₄-RE of 59% using an inlet methane load of 65 g m⁻³ h⁻¹ and a 4.8 min EBRT in a STR.

375

376 *3.3 Simultaneous methane abatement and PHB production under cyclic nitrogen feast/famine* 377 *operation*

378 Continuous PHB synthesis in a Taylor flow bioreactor under constant biogas supply
379 and sequential N feast/famine cycles was investigated under optimal EBRT and internal
380 recirculation ratio. A robust CH₄-EC, high CH₄-REs and stability in biomass concentration in
381 the bioreactor were selected as the main criteria to elucidate the optimal operational
382 conditions (i.e., an internal gas recirculation flow rate of 1.7 L min⁻¹ and an inlet flow rate of
383 0.1 L min⁻¹). Interestingly, these operational conditions provided a more robust operation
384 than an internal gas recirculation of 3.5 L min⁻¹ and inlet gas flow rate of 0.1 L min⁻¹ as a
385 result of the lower shear stress and stripping of biomass. Approximately 11 days were needed
386 to achieve steady CH₄-ECs (16.4 ± 2.9 g CH₄ m⁻³ h⁻¹) under nitrogen excess conditions in
387 stage I (Fig. 4A). These constant CH₄-ECs (15.3 ± 0.7 g CH₄ m⁻³ h⁻¹) were maintained during
388 stage II, despite the decreasing nitrogen concentrations (Fig. 4A and B). Process operation
389 under feast/famine cycles resulted in fluctuating CH₄-ECs (12.5 ± 2.0 g CH₄ m⁻³ h⁻¹) with a
390 corresponding average CH₄-RE of 46.3 ± 7.1%, which were correlated with N supply.
391 Indeed, slightly higher CH₄-ECs were recorded after MSM replacement (and therefore N
392 supply). The correlation between RCO₂ with MSM replacement during stage III was more
393 marked than that of CH₄-EC. The CH₄-ECs recorded along the three operational stages were
394 slightly lower than the values found during the mass transfer optimization assays described in
395 section 3.2 (12.5–16.4 vs. 17.1 g CH₄ m⁻³ h⁻¹). This phenomenon was attributed to the gradual
396 fouling of the membrane diffuser, which was similar to the observations of García-Pérez et al.

397 (2018) using metallic fine bubble diffusers. Additionally, the lower biomass concentrations
 398 prevailing in the Taylor flow bioreactor ($0.5\text{--}1.0\text{ g L}^{-1}$), together with a tendency to form
 399 flocs were likely responsible of the low $\text{CH}_4\text{-EC}$ herein recorded.
 400

401
 402 **Fig. 4.** Time course of (A) $\text{CH}_4\text{-EC}$ and RCO_2 ; (B) NO_2^- and NO_3^- concentration in the culture
 403 broth; and (C) biomass and PHB concentrations.

404

405 Biomass concentration experienced a gradual decrease during stage I from 1.1 to 0.6 g
 406 L^{-1} by the end of stage I (Fig. 4C). The absence of MSM replacement (and therefore culture
 407 withdrawal) during stage II resulted in an increase in biomass concentration from 0.5 to 0.98
 408 g L^{-1} . During the 14 N feast/famine cycles implemented in stage III, biomass concentration

409 slightly decreased to finally stabilize at $0.61 \pm 0.01 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ from day 43 onwards. These steady
410 state concentrations were lower than the operational conditions set during biogas
411 bioconversion into PHB in a BCB by Rodríguez et al. (2020b) ($\geq 3 \text{ g TSS L}^{-1}$) and García-
412 Pérez et al. (2018) ($\geq 4.5 \text{ g L}^{-1}$).

413 Nitrate followed an expected pattern of stable concentrations in stage I, a decreasing
414 concentration in stage II and a zigzagging concentration when implementing the feast/famine
415 cycles in stage III (Fig. 4B). Contrarily, nitrite remained always below the detection limit,
416 which prevented any inhibitory effect on methanotrophs, as previously found by Rodríguez et
417 al. (2020a).

418 The N starvation periods imposed by the feast/famine cycles induced the synthesis
419 and accumulation of bacterial PHB contents ranging from 11 to 32% (on a dry weight basis)
420 (Fig. 4C). García-Pérez et al. (2018) observed a maximum PHB concentration of 40% in *M.*
421 *hirsuta* fed with CH_4 (4%) under N feast/famine cycles of 24:48 h in a BCB with fluctuating
422 CH_4 -ECs. Rodríguez et al. (2020b) reported a maximum PHB concentration of 23% and an
423 average concentration of $\sim 15 \pm 3\%$ in a bubble column with *M. hirsuta* fed with CH_4 (9%).
424 Overall, an average PHB productivity of $5.9 \pm 2.8 \text{ g PHB m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$ (with a PHB yield of $19.8 \pm$
425 $8.5 \text{ mg PHB g CH}_4^{-1}$ and an associated specific CH_4 -EC of $0.46 \pm 0.1 \text{ g CH}_4 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ biomass d}^{-1}$)
426 was herein obtained, which was lower than those ($40\text{--}60 \text{ g PHB m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$) reported by
427 Rodríguez et al. (2020b). These differences in PHB productivities might be explained by the
428 lower dilution rates herein used (0.042 d^{-1} vs. 0.2 d^{-1}) and the lower biomass concentration
429 that prevailed in our study (~ 3 vs $\sim 0.6 \text{ g L}^{-1}$).

430

431

432

433 3.4 Bacterial diversity of the mixed methanotrophic culture

434 Molecular analyses were conducted at the beginning (inoculum) and at the end of the
435 simultaneous methane abatement and PHB production experiment in order to elucidate the
436 dynamics of the microbial communities governing the continuous CH₄ oxidation and PHB
437 accumulation bioprocess. A relatively high species evenness and richness was observed with
438 Shannon and Simpson ($1 - \lambda$) indexes of 2.86 and 3.22 and 0.88 and 0.88 for the sample
439 harvested by day 0 and day 48, respectively. Proteobacteria (now Pseudomonadota) was the
440 dominant phylum in the inoculum (75.1%), followed by Bacteroidetes (20.9%), Firmicutes
441 (2.1%) and Actinobacteria (1.3%). At the end of the 48-day experimental period, the
442 dominant phyla were Proteobacteria (53.5%), Planctomycetes (12.6%), Chloroflexi (11.6%),
443 Bacteroidetes (9.1%), Actinobacteria (8.7%) and Verrucomicrobia (3.3%). A marked
444 dominance of Proteobacteria and Bacteroidetes has been previously reported in obligate
445 mixed methanotrophic consortia enriched from different environments such as landfill top
446 cover and compost soils (Chidambarampadmavathy et al., 2017), *Sphagnum* mosses (Pérez et
447 al., 2019b), marine sediments (Chidambarampadmavathy et al., 2017). At the genus level, as
448 shown in Fig. 5, the dominant genera in the inoculum included *Methylocystis* (53.4%),
449 *Chryseobacterium* (7.0%), *Sediminibacterium* (5.7%), *Achromobacter* (4.5%), *Sphingomonas*
450 (3.5%), *Methylobacterium* (3.4%), *Pseudarcicella* (2.4%), *Brevundimonas* (2.2%),
451 *Sphingosinicella* (1.6%), *Hyphomicrobium* (1.3%), *Lutispora* (1.0%). Comparatively, the
452 dominant bacterial genera at the end of bioreactor operation were *Methylocystis* (31.9%),
453 *Hyphomicrobium* (8.4%), *Rubinisphaeraceae* SH PL14 (7.5%), *Pseudonocardia* (5.3%),
454 *Phycisphaeraceae* SM1A02 (3.4%), *Microscillaceae* OLB12 (3.4%), *Neochlamydia* (3.2%),
455 *Fuscovulum* (2.7%), *Hydrogenophaga* (2.6%), *Taibaiella* (2.3%), *Aeromicrobium* (1.5%),

456 *Xanthobacter* (1.3%), *Niabella* (1.3%), which together accounted for $\approx 75\%$ of total bacterial
 457 community (Fig. 5).

458
 459 **Fig. 5.** Taxonomic diversity at the genus level of the mixed methanotrophic culture at time zero
 460 (inoculum) and at the end of the PHB accumulation experiment. Top 70 dominant bacteria
 461 were graphed while other bacterial taxa were grouped as “Others”. LCDB: Local contribution
 462 to beta-diversity.

463
 464 It is noteworthy to highlight that type II methanotrophs outcompeted non-PHB
 465 accumulating type I methanotrophs despite the use of nitrate as the nitrogen source.
 466 *Methylocystis* was the only type II methanotroph and the most dominant bacteria detected
 467 throughout the Taylor flow bioreactor operation, which suggested that it was the main
 468 responsible of the simultaneous CH₄ abatement and PHB accumulation process. The presence
 469 of *Methylocystis* in the process can be well-explained by the type of microbial consortia used
 470 as the inoculum source, which were enriched in *Methylocystis* spp. when grown at 25°C

471 under an O₂- and CH₄-rich atmosphere and phosphorus/nitrogen limiting conditions (Pérez et
472 al., 2019a, 2019b), and by the bioaugmentation strategy performed with *Methylocystis hirsuta*
473 CSC1 (Rodríguez et al., 2020a). The use of nitrate as the nitrogen source may have also
474 contributed to the dominance of *Methylocystis* in the mixed methanotrophic consortium
475 (Kulkarni et al., 2022).

476 On the other hand, *Hyphomicrobium* is a heterotrophic denitrifier, facultative
477 methylotroph able to grow on C1 and C2 compounds and accumulate PHA under nitrogen
478 limitation (Cao et al., 2021; Fergala et al., 2018; Myung et al., 2015). It is well-known that
479 co-occurring bacteria in methanotrophic consortia can grow on excreted CH₄ degradation
480 metabolites (Carmona-Martínez et al., 2021; Salem et al., 2021), some of which might be
481 toxic for methanotrophs. The co-occurrence of the type II methanotroph *Methylocystis* (ca.
482 55–80%) and the methylotroph *Hyphomicrobium* (ca. 5–10%) genera in heterotrophic-
483 methanotrophic consortia has been previously reported (Chidambarampadmavathy et al.,
484 2017; Fergala et al., 2018; Myung et al., 2015). Thus, Jeong and Kim (2019) argued that co-
485 culturing of *Hyphomicrobium* and *Methylocystis* can produce an efficient and stable methane
486 oxidation system, in which *Hyphomicrobium* improved the methane-oxidation rate and
487 biomass growth due to cross-feeding of CH₄-derived carbon intermediates produced by
488 *Methylocystis*. Thus, it was hypothesized that *Hyphomicrobium* might have played a
489 synergistic action in the mixed methanotrophic culture not only by removing putative toxic
490 by-products for *Methylocystis* but also by co-producing PHB under nitrogen limitation. In
491 this context, a recent study by Salem et al.(2021) reported that the enrichment of type II
492 methanotrophs with other PHB producers such as *Pseudomonas* may lead to a synergic PHB
493 accumulation effect.

494 On the other hand, some *Pseudonocardia* spp. are known to degrade aliphatic
495 hydrocarbons such as toluene (Juteau et al., 1999) and to growth on C1 compounds such as
496 formate, methanol and carbon monoxide as the sole carbon and energy source (Groster et al.,
497 2013). Indeed, the actinobacterial genus *Pseudonocardia* has been detected in
498 methanotrophic consortia (Burrows et al., 2021), but its role on the PHB-producing
499 methanotrophic reactor remains unknown. Similarly, the role of *Rubinisphaeraceae* SH PL14
500 on the performance of the bioreactor is also unclear. To the best of the author's knowledge,
501 this is the first report of *Rubinisphaeraceae* SH PL14 in a methanotrophic accumulating PHB
502 system. It should be noted that satellite bacteria (< 1%) may exert a significant effect on the
503 overall process, and they may even become dominant depending on the bioreactor
504 operational conditions. Further studies are needed for a better understanding of the
505 interactions and cooperation between methanotrophs and heterotrophs driving the
506 simultaneous CH₄ abatement and PHAs production.

507

508 *3.5 Implications and future perspectives*

509 To the best of the authors knowledge, this study was the first work performed in a high-
510 mass-transfer Taylor flow bioreactor, which represents an important contribution to the state-
511 of-the-art PHB production using biogas as feedstock. However, further research must be
512 conducted to optimize this innovative technology platform. First, the long-term operation and
513 production of PHB using mixed cultures needs to be further assessed in terms of stability of
514 the bioreactor performance and microbial population structure. In this regard, (Helm et al.,
515 2006) achieved a more stable community structure under a long-term operation (29 months
516 and under phosphate limiting conditions) than the work herein presented. Secondly, new
517 feast/famine cycling strategies must be tested to find the optimal conditions that ensure

518 simultaneously a high methane abatement and PHB productivities, and a stable biomass
519 growth in high mass transfer bioreactors (Rodríguez et al., 2020c). In this context, it is
520 imperative to assess the feasibility of continuous process operation in a single- or multi-stage
521 reactors capable of supporting a simultaneous methanotrophic biomass growth, methane
522 abatement and PHB synthesis (Rodríguez, 2022). Finally, the addition of valerate to trigger
523 the synthesis of tailored PHAs (i.e. PHBV) should be considered in order to make this
524 process more attractive from biorefinery point of view (Cal et al., 2016; López et al., 2018).

525

526 **4. Conclusions**

527 The continuous biogas-based PHB production by a mixed methanotrophic culture
528 grown under constant biogas supply, cyclic N starvation and Taylor flow regime was
529 investigated. This is the first proof-of-concept study showing the feasibility of producing
530 biopolymers from biogas in an engineered Taylor flow bioreactor, which is a reactor
531 configuration characterized for sustaining relatively high mass transfer rates at a relative low
532 energy consumption. The applied internal gas recycling strategy enabled the decoupling of
533 the gas residence time from the turbulence inside the reactor, leading to a better CH₄
534 abatement performance in terms of CH₄-RE. The Taylor flow regime and N-limiting
535 conditions supported CH₄-REs of $\approx 50\%$ and CH₄-ECs of $\approx 12.5 \text{ g CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$, while the PHB
536 content ranged from 11 to 32% $w w^{-1}$ of the CDW, which resulted in average PHB
537 productivities of $\approx 6 \text{ g PHB m}^{-3} \text{ d}^{-1}$. The molecular analyses revealed that type II
538 methanotrophs outcompeted type I methanotrophs despite the high diversity found in the
539 microbial community. *Methylocystis* was identified as the key PHB producer.

540

541

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551

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